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FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF MUCOADHESIVE MICROSPHERES OF ORAL HYPOGLYCEMIC DRUG

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ABSTRACT

Mucoadhesive microspheres were found to be more efficient for controlled drug delivery. Mucoadhesion ensures increased contact time of the dosage form with the absorption site while microspheres sustained the release of drug from the dosage form at the site of absorption and result into improved bioavailability of drug. The present study involves formulation and evaluation of mucoadhesive microspheres of oral hypoglycemic drug, metformin hydrochloride. The microspheres were formulated by emulsification phase separation technique using chitosan as polymer and gluteraldehyde as cross-linking agent. Preformulation studies showed that the compositions are compatible with each other. The formulation batches were prepared by 3² factorial design with two independent parameters, polymer to drug ratio and stirring speed. All the batches were evaluated for particle size, flow properties, mucoadhesion, microencapsulation efficiency, drug release and stability. The formulation MF5 showed nearly spherical microcapsules, good flowability, microencapsulation efficiency, mucoadhesion, stability and extended drug release upto 12 hours. An approach to develop a stable mucoadhesive microspheres of oral hypoglycemic drug, Metformin hydrochloride has been successfully achieved.

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INTRODUCTION

Microencapsulation is a process by which the droplets or particles of liquid or solid material are surrounded or coated with a continuous film of polymeric material, resulting into the capsules ranging from less than one micron to several hundred microns in size. Microcapsules may be spherical in shape, with a continuous wall surrounding the core, while others are asymmetrically and variably shaped. These microspheres or microparticles or microcapsules can be prepared by using natural or synthetic polymers. [1] The most acceptable and convenient method of drug administration is the oral route because of its ease of administration. One limitation related with the oral delivery is poor bioavailability and for the drug candidates who show absorption window in the proximal gut and is the major obstacle to the development of controlled release formulation. [2] Mucoadhesive microspheres is one of such advances in drug delivery system which ensure the drug targeting and retention at the site of absorption to facilitate contact between the dosage form and absorption surface to improve the bioavailability of drug. The main objective of this delivery system is to control the release profile of drug and also to sustain the drug release. Bioadhesive microspheres have major advantages like efficient absorption and enhanced bioavailability of the drugs due to a high surface to volume ratio, a much more intimate contact with the mucus layer and specific targeting of drugs to the absorption site. [3] Microencapsulation has been accepted as a process to achieve controlled release. The selection of the technique for the preparation of microcapsules depends on many factors such as the drug solubility and short half-life of drug. Present study is related with the development of mucoadhesive microspheres of Metformin hydrochloride which resulted into sustained and localized release of the drug in the stomach.

Diabetes (Diabetes mellitus) is a metabolism disorder has a condition in which the quantity of glucose in the blood is too elevated and it's characterized by chronic hyperglycemia with disturbances of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism resulting from defects in insulin secretion, and it may present with characteristic symptoms such as thirst, polyuria, blurring of vision, weight loss, risk of cardiovascular, peripheral vascular and cerebrovascular disease etc., which is controlled by using anti-diabetic drugs. Metformin hydrochloride is a widely used biguanide hypoglycemic drug for the management of non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus. It is used as monotherapy as an adjunct to diet and exercise for the management of type 2 (non-insulin dependent) diabetes. Metformin hydrochloride improves glucose tolerance in patients with type 2 diabetes, which decreases blood glucose levels by decreasing hepatic glucose production, decreases intestinal absorption of glucose and improving insulin sensitivity by increasing peripheral glucose uptake and utilization.

A conventional dose of 500 mg metformin hydrochloride can control glucose level 6-8 hours and high dose of metformin hydrochloride may cause Vitamin B12 deficiency due to interference with its absorption. The site of metformin hydrochloride absorption is stomach and upper part of intestine whereas at the colon it is poorly absorbed. Further it has short biological half-life of 1.5-3 hours which results into quick elimination of drug from blood circulation and low bioavailability of 50-60%. By incorporating the drug metformin hydrochloride into microcapsules the approach has been made to ensure the reduction in overdose side effects, availability of the drug at absorption site (stomach) for prolonged time, increased bioavailability of drug by sustaining the release of drug at the site of absorption. Therefore it is the requirement of the time to prepare mucoadhesive sustained release dosage form of the drug, which will ensure the availability of drug at the site of absorption for prolonged time. [5]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The Metformin hydrochloride was obtained as gift sample from Aurobindo pharma Ltd. Hyderabad. Chitosan was obtained as gift samples from Wockhardt Ltd. Aurangabad. All the other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Methods

Characterization of drug

Metformin hydrochloride was characterized by determining its solubility, melting point, UV curve, IR spectrum and DSC graph.

UV method validation of selected drug

The UV method development was done by determining λ_{\max} , precision, recovery, LOD, LOQ, linearity and by preparing calibration curve. [6-8]

Preliminary compatibility study

The compatibility study of the selected drug and polymers was studied by Differential scanning calorimetry and Infra-red spectroscopy.

Preparation of microspheres of Metformin hydrochloride

Preparation of mucoadhesive microspheres of Metformin hydrochloride was done by Emulsification phase separation technique. The microspheres were formulated by using different polymer drug ratio and glutaraldehyde as crosslinking agent. [9]

Table I: Factorial batches of Metformin hydrochloride.

Sr. No.	Batch Code	Polymer : Drug	Stirring Speed (rpm)
1	MF1	1 : 1	500
2	MF2	1 : 1	1000
3	MF3	1 : 1	1500
4	MF4	3 : 1	500
5	MF5	3 : 1	1000
6	MF6	3 : 1	1500
7	MF7	6 : 1	500
8	MF8	6 : 1	1000
9	MF9	6 : 1	1500

Preparation of microspheres

The required quantity of Chitosan was dissolved in 150ml 1%v/v aqueous acetic acid solution. To this solution the required quantity of drug was dispersed. Later this solution was extruded through syringe no. 20 in a container containing 1 liter of liquid paraffin (heavy and light in 1:1 ratio) and 0.2% Dioctyl sodium sulfosuccinate (DOSS) to reduce aggregation of microspheres, with continuous stirring at required speed. The stirring was continued for 15 min. to this mixture 50ml of 25% v/v aqueous glutaraldehyde was added and stirring was done for one hour. After one hour the microspheres were filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether to remove oil. Then the microspheres were washed with excess water to remove glutaraldehyde. The prepared microspheres were dried at room temperature for 24 hours. [10]

Evaluation of mucoadhesive microspheres of Metformin hydrochloride

Physical properties determination

The particle size of the microspheres was determined by using optical microscopy method using a pre-calibrated ocular micrometer and stage micrometer. [11] The surface of the microspheres for morphological characterization were observed via scanning electron microscopy. The flow properties of prepared microspheres were determined by bulk density, angle of repose, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio. [12]

Estimation of drug content

Metformin hydrochloride content in the microcapsules was estimated by a UV spectrophotometric method based on the measurement of absorbance at 204 nm in 0.1N HCl.

Percentage yield

The batches were weighed after drying and the yield % was calculated using the formula given below

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{W}{W_t} \times 100$$

Where,

W= Practical Weight of prepared microspheres

W_t= Original weight of drug and polymers [13]

Micro-encapsulation efficiency

The prepared microspheres equivalent to 10 mg of Metformin hydrochloride were weighed accurately and crushed. The powdered microspheres were placed in 10 ml of 0.1N HCL and kept for 24 hours. The solution was then filtered and solution was diluted with fresh solvent and absorbance was measured at 204 nm using UV spectrophotometer and the percent drug entrapped was calculated as follows: [14]

$$\% \text{Drug entrapment} = \frac{\text{Calculated Drug Content}}{\text{Theoretical Drug Content}} \times 100$$

In-vitro Wash-off test for microspheres

The mucoadhesive properties of the microspheres were evaluated by in vitro wash-off test. A 3X2 cm piece of goat intestine mucosa was tied onto a glass slide using thread. Weighed microspheres were spread onto the wet rinsed tissue specimen, and the prepared slide was hung onto one of the grooves of a USP tablet disintegrating test apparatus as shown in "Figure 2". The disintegrating test apparatus were operated such that the tissue specimen was given regular up and down movements in a beaker containing 0.1N HCl. At the end of 1, 4 and 8 hours the weight of microspheres still adhering onto the tissue was determined after centrifugation and drying. [15]

$$\% \text{ Mucoadhesion} = \frac{\text{Wt of microspheres adhered}}{\text{Wt of microspheres applied}} \times 100$$

Figure 1: Goat intestine mucosa.

Figure 2: In-vitro Wash-off test.

In-vitro drug release

In vitro release studies were carried in 0.1N HCl medium. The test conditions are as follows: microspheres containing 100 mg of drug packed in a capsule were placed in baskets in a vessel containing 900 ml of 0.1N HCl medium with the temperature maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The rotating rate of the basket was adjusted to 50 rpm. With intervals of one hour, 5 ml of samples were withdrawn and filtered through a $0.45\mu\text{m}$ membrane filter. The equivalent volume of the medium with the same temperature was added to the dissolution vessel to maintain sink condition. The absorbance values of the filtrate at the wavelength of 204 nm were determined and percent drug release calculated. [16, 17]

Comparison of release profile with conventional tablet

The release profile of the selected batch was compared with the conventional Metformin hydrochloride tablet (Glyciphage tablet: Metformin tablet IP 500mg).

Stability study

Stability studies were carried out according to International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The optimized batch MF5 was stored at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 75 \pm 5\%$ RH (relative humidity) for three months. The samples were withdrawn and evaluated for drug content, average particle size, percent muco-adhesion after 8 hours and drug release. [18]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mucoadhesive microspheres of Metformin hydrochloride by using chitosan as polymer and glutaraldehyde as crosslinking agent were prepared by emulsification phase separation technique. The optimization of the batches was done by 3^2 factorial design considering two independent factors as polymer to drug ratio and stirring speed.

The purity of drug sample was confirmed by determination of its melting point, solubility, λ_{\max} , DSC and IR spectrum. The melting point of the drug was found to be 222°C which is between the standard range of $222 - 226^\circ\text{C}$. The λ_{\max} of Metformin hydrochloride in 0.1N HCL was found to be 204 nm. The DSC and IR peaks were found to be similar with the standard DSC and IR peaks of the pure drug.

Figure 3: UV spectrum of Metformin hydrochloride in 0.1N HCL.

Figure 4: DSC thermogram of Metformin hydrochloride.

The UV method validation for estimation of drug Metformin hydrochloride in 0.1N HCL was done successfully with linearity, precision, recovery, LOD and LOQ. The λ_{\max} was found to be 204 nm and the calibration curve was plotted as follow:

Table II: Calibration curve of Metformin hydrochloride in 0.1N HCl.

Sr. No.	Concentration (mcg/ml)	Absorbance
1	2	0.28
2	4	0.49
3	6	0.68
4	8	0.88
5	10	1.09
6	12	1.30

Figure 5: Standard curve of Metformin hydrochloride.

The compatibility study between drug and polymers selected was done by the DSC and IR. There were no much significant changes observed between the DSC thermogram and IR spectrum of pure drug and that of the mixtures of drug and polymers.

Average particle size of microspheres of all the batches were found to be in the range of 88 to 189 μm . the surface morphology of the microspheres indicated that the spheres are nearly spherical and have rough surface "Figure 6". The flowability of particles depending upon the parameters such as angle of repose, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio was from good to excellent (table III).

Figure 6: SEM image of MF5 batch.

Table III: Physical properties of factorial batches.

Sr. No.	Batch code	Average particle size (μm)	Angle of repose	Carr's index	Hausner ratio	% Micro-encapsulation efficiency
1	MF1	102.5 \pm 3.45	38.72 \pm 0.56	16.02 \pm 0.16	1.17 \pm 0.09	85.36
2	MF2	95.62 \pm 2.72	40.35 \pm 0.25	17.16 \pm 0.05	1.20 \pm 0.02	83.04
3	MF3	88.21 \pm 1.76	41.42 \pm 0.36	17.63 \pm 0.15	1.21 \pm 0.05	85.48
4	MF4	140.55 \pm 2.03	33.4 \pm 0.08	14.52 \pm 0.20	1.16 \pm 0.08	89.72
5	MF5	128.64 \pm 1.05	33.57 \pm 0.16	15.80 \pm 0.14	1.17 \pm 0.06	95.4
6	MF6	125.16 \pm 0.87	37.64 \pm 0.73	16.26 \pm 0.08	1.18 \pm 0.05	88.8
7	MF7	184.72 \pm 2.84	30.63 \pm 0.18	14.04 \pm 0.06	1.16 \pm 0.04	90.86
8	MF8	181.7 \pm 4.08	32.06 \pm 0.28	14.85 \pm 0.17	1.16 \pm 0.08	87.78
9	MF9	173.19 \pm 3.64	35.15 \pm 0.85	15.36 \pm 0.15	1.16 \pm 0.12	95.2

Percent estimated drug content of the factorial batches varied from 12.54 to 42.74%. The percent micro-encapsulation efficiency of the batches are shown in table III. Mucoadhesion was studied by in-vitro wash-off test upto 8 hours and the microspheres showed good mucoadhesion as shown in table IV.

Table IV: In-vitro wash-off test.

Sr. No.	Batch code	Percent Mucoadhesion		
		1 Hour	4 Hour	8 Hour
1	MF1	85.14	79.23	76.14
2	MF2	84.15	80.26	76.92
3	MF3	83.82	79.09	74.86
4	MF4	86.66	82.81	80.23
5	MF5	87.3	84.01	80.57
6	MF6	86.52	82.07	79.48
7	MF7	88.54	86.18	83.47
8	MF8	90.26	86.11	83.54
9	MF9	88.24	84.9	82.33

In-vitro drug release from the factorial batches was slow and controlled. The study revealed that with increase in particle size the release of drug decreased as particle size increases surface area decreases and diffusional path length increases which results in slow drug release, and vice-versa with decrease in particle size. With increase in stirring speed, the particle size decreased which resulted in faster drug release. The drug release from the factorial batches are graphically represented in figure 7, 8 and 9.

Figure 7: Percent drug release from batches MF1, MF2 and MF3.

Figure 8: Percent drug release from batches MF4, MF5 and MF6.

Figure 9: Percent drug release from batches MF7, MF8 and MF9.

The release profile of the optimized batch MF5 when compared with marketed conventional tablet, was found to be prolonged for 12 hours.

Figure 10: Percent drug release from batch MF5 and marketed tablet (Glyciphage).

Table V: Stability study of MF5 batch.

Sr. No.	Parameters	MF5	
		0 month	3month
1	Drug content (%)	19.4	18.85
2	Particle size	128.64 ± 1.05	131.82 ± 0.94
3	% Mucoadhesion after 8 hours	80.57	81.21
4	Drug release after 12 hours	89.01 ± 1.00	90.26 ± 0.78

The stability study of the optimized batch MF5 indicated no significant changes in drug content, average particle size, mucoadhesion and drug release.

CONCLUSION

An attempt has been made to develop a stable mucoadhesive microparticulate system of drug Metformin hydrochloride using Chitosan by emulsification phase separation technique. The variables polymer to drug ratio and stirring speed exhibited significant effect on the release profile of drug and mucoadhesion of microspheres. With increase in concentration of polymer the increase in particle size was observed which resulted in slower drug release but with increase in stirring speed the particle size decreased which resulted in increased surface area and decreased diffusional path length thus increase in the rate of drug release. The optimized batch MF5 was found to be best batch among all the factorial batches, since it showed good flow ability, mucoadhesion, fair drug entrapment and it could prolong the release of drug for longer duration. The drug release from MF5 was found to be prolonged for 12 hours whereas the release from the conventional marketed tablet ends within 5 hours. A stable mucoadhesive microspheres of oral hypoglycemic drug, Metformin hydrochloride has been successfully developed by emulsification phase separation technique.

Future research

In-vivo study
IVIVC establishment

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